

Lower Turonian inoceramid bivalve of the genus *Mytiloides* Brongniart, 1822 from Maghra El Hadida Formation, north Eastern Desert, Egypt

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Abstract

In the Cenomanian–Turonian sequence of Egypt, inoceramid bivalves are extremely scarce. Two lower Turonian (Upper Cretaceous) inoceramid bivalves of the genus *Mytiloides* Brongniart, from the north Eastern Desert, Egypt, are systematically described. The studied material comes from one stratigraphic section from Wadi Umm Khayshar, northern Galala Plateau, Wadi Araba. The labiatoid *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz) of the group of *Mytiloides labiatus* (Schlotheim) and the subquadrate *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban (*Mytiloides hattini* group) are identified herein, the last species being identified and described systematically for the first time from Egypt. According to current state of knowledge on the Egyptian ammonite biozonation, the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary coincides with the last occurrence of the ammonoids *Vascoceras cauvini* Chudeau and the first appearance of *Vascoceras proprium* (Reyment). The first occurrence of *M. kossmati* is coincident with that of *V. proprium* (Reyment) and *M. puebloensis* and allows precise placement of the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the area under study. Biostratigraphic and paleogeographic implications of the identified *Mytiloides*, and the associated ammonites, are also discussed.

Keywords

Mytiloides, inoceramid bivalves, taxonomy, biostratigraphy, lower Turonian, Egypt.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Cenomanian–Turonian sequence of Egypt provide diverse macrofaunal assemblages (bivalves, gastropods, cephalopods, and echinoids), including ammonoids of special significance. Unfortunately, inoceramid bivalves are quite rare in the Cenomanian–Turonian successions of Egypt. Worldwide, the Cretaceous inoceramid bivalves were extensively dispersed and represent one of the most significant faunal elements of the period. Paleogeographically, the Cretaceous inoceramid bivalves did not thrive in very shallow or very warm seas and are therefore rare in Tethyan shallow water deposits. Most inoceramid groups were cosmopolitan during the Albian–Cenomanian interval. Dhondt (1992) concluded that, from the Turonian onwards, the North Pacific Province is characterized by endemic inoceramid faunas and following the opening of the South Atlantic Ocean in the Turonian, new inoceramid lineages in the Southern Hemisphere from Brazil to Madagascar evolved, in co-

occurrence with other cosmopolitan groups. One of the most significant faunal components during Turonian times is represented by the genus *Mytiloides* Brongniart, 1822, which was distributed worldwide. Many workers were concerned with the fossil invertebrates of the Cenomanian–Turonian successions of Egypt (e.g. Douvillé, 1928; Luger & Gröschke, 1989; Kassab, 1985, 1994, 1996; Aly & Abdel-Gawad, 2001; El-Hedeny & Nafee, 2001; El-Hedeny, 2002; Hewaidy *et al.*, 2003, 2012; Abdel-Gawad *et al.*, 2004, 2006, 2007; El Qot, 2006, 2008; Nagm, 2009; Nagm *et al.*, 2010a, 2019; Nagm & Wilmsen, 2012; El-Sabbagh *et al.*, 2011; Ayoub-Hannaa & Fürsich, 2012a; Moneer, 2015; Abdel-Raheem *et al.*, 2020; Abdelhady *et al.*, 2021; Abd-Elhameed *et al.*, 2023; Aly *et al.*, 2023).

The first finding of the upper Cenomanian inoceramid bivalves from Egypt dates back to the early twentieth century, when Blankenhorn (1900, p. 38) documented “*Inoceramus Cripsi*, Mantell, 1822” from Beadnell’s collection from the Bahariya Oasis, Western Desert,

Egypt (see Seibertz, 1996, p. 317 for a further discussion). Awad & Abdallah (1966, p. 134), on the other hand, recorded the first Egyptian lower Turonian inoceramid bivalve "*Inoceramus labiatus* (Schlotheim, 1913)" from the footslope of Gebel Thelmet in the Southern Galala Plateau. Seibertz (1996) fully discussed the endemic and cosmopolitan inoceramid bivalves from the upper Cretaceous of Egypt, including their stratigraphic evidence and regional occurrences. Recently in the last two decades, few investigations have been conducted on the Cenomanian–Turonian inoceramid bivalves of Egypt. Abdel-Gawad *et al.* (2004) figured one specimen from the upper Cenomanian Abu Qada Formation, eastern Sinai and systematically identified it as *Inoceramus* ex. gr. *Inoceramus pictus* J. de C. Sowerby, 1829. El Qot (2006) studied three specimens from the upper Cenomanian successions of the East Themed area, east Central Sinai and tentatively assigned them to *Inoceramus pictus*. Mekawy (2007) identified the Middle Cenomanian *Inoceramus* cf. *atlanticus* (Heinz, 1936) and the lower Turonian *Inoceramus* (*Mytiloides*) *labiatus* (Schlotheim) from Galala Plateau, north Eastern Desert, Egypt. Nagm (2009) described and identified two inoceramid species from the lower Turonian sequences of Wadi Araba, northern Eastern Desert: *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz, 1930) and *Mytiloides labiatus*. Nagm *et al.* (2011) described and illustrated a single inoceramid bivalve co-occurred with the ammonoid *Neolobites vibrayanus* (d'Orbigny, 1841) from the lower upper Cenomanian shallow-water deposits of the Galala Formation (Wadi Qena, Eastern Desert). The studied specimen is tentatively assigned to *Inoceramus pictus* group. *Mytiloides concentricus* Parkinson, 1819 was recorded by Ayoub-Hannaa & Fürsich (2012b) from eastern Sinai, Egypt, but it was neither illustrated nor described. Nagm (2015) in his interesting study on the stratigraphic significance of the rapid faunal change across the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the Eastern Desert, Egypt, recorded and figured the lower Turonian inoceramid bivalve *Mytiloides kossmati*. Due to the poorly preserved posterior margin of the material described, Abdel-Raheem *et al.* (2020) doubtfully described *Mytiloides labiatus* from the Southern Galala Plateau (Eastern Desert, Egypt). The two inoceramid bivalves *Mytiloides kossmati* and *Mytiloides labiatus* were also recorded, without illustrations or description, from the lower Turonian successions of the northern Eastern Desert of Egypt by El-Sabbagh *et al.* (2021). The present work focuses on the description, identification, systematic classification and paleobiogeographic implications of two inoceramid specimens, and the associated fauna, that have been collected from the lower Turonian stratigraphic section at Wadi Umm Khayshar, Wadi Araba, northern Galala Plateau, northern Eastern Desert, Egypt (Fig. 1).

2. GEOLOGIC SETTING

In the Cretaceous period, Egypt was situated at the southern margin of the Eastern Mediterranean Basin, at the northern boundary of the African plate. Egypt was subjected to four processes of marine transgression during the Cretaceous period: Aptian, Cenomanian, Coniacian, and Campanian–Maastrichtian (Said, 1990). Major transgressions occurred in Egypt during the Cenomanian age. According to sedimentary evidence, marine conditions predominated in northern Egypt during the early Cenomanian and spread to the southern part of the country during the late Cenomanian (El Hawat, 1997). The Cenomanian succession in Egypt was composed of marine siliciclastics mixed with carbonates, which were characterized by benthic foraminifera, bivalves, gastropods, echinoids, and particularly the upper Cenomanian ammonoids of *Neolobites*, *Thomelites*, and *Vascoceras*. In the Turonian, sea-level rise continued and many areas were flooded with strata very rich in planktonic foraminifera and ammonoids (*Choffaticeras*, *Wrightoceras* and *Coilopoceras*). The peak of the late Turonian regression, which was centered at about 90 Ma in Egypt, was caused by worldwide tectonic events linked to volcanic activity and intrusions of alkaline volcanic rocks (Meneisy, 1990).

The Cenomanian–Turonian interval reflects probably the most pronounced Cretaceous transgression in northeastern Egypt, with maximum flooding occurring during the early Turonian. The Egyptian Eastern Desert's Southern Galala Plateau (longitudes 31°40' to 32°35' E and latitudes 29°10' N to 28°15' N and) is located in the northern region of the country (Fig. 1). The Wadi Araba to the north and the Gulf of Suez to the east define this region. It stretches west to the central Eocene limestone plateau and south to Wadi Qena's northern end. The study area follows the path of the regional Syrian Arc anticline structure, which runs NE–SW. The Syrian Arc, one of northern Egypt's most prominent structural features (Said, 1990), runs from Syria to Egypt's central Western Desert, passing via Sinai and the northern section of the Eastern Desert. The Galala plateaus, which form a significant branch of the Syrian Arc in the Eastern Desert, experienced Late Cretaceous uplift in the north and subsidence in the south. The Syrian Arc began to fold and/or uplift after the Cenomanian age (Aal & Lelek, 1994) and reached its peak activity during the Late Cretaceous Epoch (Kuss *et al.*, 2000; Rosenthal *et al.*, 2000). Strong siliciclastic input at Wadi Qena and the absence of marine layers to the south indicate that the shoreline was located immediately south of the study region. A vast pericontinental shelf sea covered extensive portions of Sinai and the Eastern Desert during the late Cenomanian, as demonstrated by the deposition of thick shallow-marine sediments. Transgression moved southward throughout the early and middle Turonian, and the deposits of shelf sea increased (Nagm, 2009). According

Fig. 1: A geological map of the studied area with the locality of the measured section (modified after Conoco, 1987).

to Wilmsen & Nagm (2012), following subaerial exposure of the Galala Formation in the mid-Late Cenomanian, a major transgressive facies development occurred during the late Late Cenomanian, resulting in the development of an open-marine carbonate system represented by the uppermost Cenomanian-Turonian Maghra el Hadida Formation marls and limestones. On the study area, the shallow-marine Galala Formation and the deep-subtidal to intertidal Maghra El Hadida Formation are well exposed and representing examples of this transgression in the Eastern Desert.

3. STRATIGRAPHIC FRAMEWORK

In the northeastern Desert (where the study area is located), Cretaceous sediments characterize the area north of latitude $27^{\circ}25' E$ and extend northward to $30^{\circ}19' N$ (Issawi *et al.*, 1999). The Cenomanian-Turonian successions are widely distributed in Egypt and well exposed, especially in the central and north Eastern Desert. The stratigraphy of the exposed Cenomanian-Turonian strata in the north Eastern Desert has been the subject of numerous studies, including Abdallah & Adindani (1963), El-Akkad & Abdallah (1971), Kora *et al.* (2001), Nagm *et al.* (2010a, b), Hewaidy *et al.* (2012), Moneer (2015) and others. The Cenomanian-Turonian

successions in study area has been classified, from base to top, into the following rock units: Malha Formation (pre Cenomanian), Galala Formation (Cenomanian) and Maghra El Hadida Formation (Turonian).

The Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section is the most complete section in Wadi Araba, 57 km to the west of El Zaafarana (see Fig. 1; Fig. 3A). A stratigraphic section of 150 m was measured and sampled in detail, located at the northern slope of the southern Galala Plateau (Long. 32°9'13" E and Lat. 28°51'48" N). The basal part of the measured stratigraphic section is dominated mainly by highly ferruginous and botryoidal sandstones, with abundant, mostly fragmented and crushed silicified wood. These sandstone beds are assigned to the Malha Formation. However, excluding the presence of the silicified wood, the Malha Formation is considered as non-fossiliferous rock unit of unknown age, and assigned herein as pre-Cenomanian. The measured thickness of the uppermost part of the Malha Formation cropping out in Wadi Umm Khayshar is about 30 m (Fig. 2). It consists mainly of coarse-grained, highly ferruginous, cross-bedded sandstone, unconformably overlain by greenish fine grained shaley marls of the Cenomanian Galala Formation (Fig. 3B, C). The contact between these two rock units can be easily recognized in the field by the change in grain size and color of lithology and the high fossil content of the Galala Formation. The total thickness of the Galala Formation in the measured section is about 52 m, poorly fossiliferous and highly bioturbated at the base (see Fig. 2). These poorly fossiliferous beds are followed by 25 m thick of greenish fine-grained silty marl that overlain by highly fossiliferous greenish fine-grained shaley marl beds of about 22 m thickness. This part of the Galala Formation is characterized by an abundance of different typical Cenomanian oyster and gastropod species (Fig. 3D, E). *Neolobites vibrayanus* (d'Orbigny, 1841) and *Thomelites* aff. *sornayi* (Thomel, 1966) are two ammonoid species recovered from this stratigraphic level. The uppermost part of the upper Cenomanian Galala Formation is consisting of greenish fine grained shaley marl rich in ammonoids (*Vascoceras gamai* Choffat, 1898 and *Vascoceras cauvini* Chudeau, 1909) with frequent occurrences of rudist bivalves, echinoids, and sponges. About 4 m of cross-bedded, non-fossiliferous sandstones characterize the topmost part of the Galala Formation in the measured section, conformably overlaid by the Turonian Maghra El Hadida Formation.

In Wadi Umm Khayshar, the total measured thickness of Maghra El Hadida Formation is 97 m, its basal part being marked by 3 m of white to yellowish, fine-grained calcareous sandstone that contain the ammonoid *Vascoceras proprium* (Reyment, 1954), assigned to an early Turonian. The *Vascoceras proprium* bed lies beneath 10 m of greenish fine-grained marlstone densely packed with complete preserved shells, and some crushed, eroded Turonian *Choffaticeras* spp. The lower Turonian in Wadi

Umm Khayshar is marked by a very diagnostic bed that could be informally described as the "ammonoid" or the *Choffaticeras* bed" (Fig. 3F, G; Figs 7, 8). The *Choffaticeras* bed contains abundant *Choffaticeras* species, including *Choffaticeras (Choffaticeras) meslei* (Peron, 1897), *Choffaticeras (Leoniceras) luciae* (Pervinquier, 1907), and *Choffaticeras (Choffaticeras) segne* (Solger, 1903). Above the *Choffaticeras* bed, about 17.5 m thick of white and greenish fine-grained limestone, shaley limestone and marl characterized by highly abundant and highly diversified fauna including typical lower Turonian echinoids, gastropods, bivalves and the ammonoids [*Neoptchytes cephalotus* (Courtillet, 1860), *Thomasites* cf. *rollandi* (Thomas & Peron, 1889), *Wrightoceras muniri* (Pervinquier, 1907)]. These beds with their faunal association are directly overlined by a thick clastic succession with a total thickness exceeding 48 m, formed mainly of yellowish fine-grained siliclastic rocks (siltstone, shale, and sandstone), totally unfossiliferous which represent the middle Turonian. This clastic unit is conformably followed by a 10 m thick bed of white to yellowish white, fine-grained limestone containing the typical late Turonian ammonoid, *Coilopoceras requianum* (d'Orbigny, 1841).

4. SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Repositories of specimens: The following abbreviations are used to indicate the repositories of specimens cited in the text: Geological Museum of Aswan University (repository GMAU). **Conventions:** The abbreviations used for the localities are Wadi Umm Khayshar (Kh). BI-231 is a Bivalvia specimen number 231. All linear dimensions, taken with a Vernier Caliper, are given in millimeters. The abbreviations used for inoceramid bivalve morphology and biometry are: L = Shell length, H = Shell height, S = hinge line length, h = axial length, I = secondary axis, BH = beak height (see Fig. 4).

Systematics: *Mytiloides* is classified according to Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000. Higher taxonomy follows Carter *et al.* (2011).

Superfamily Inoceramoidea Giebel, 1852

Family Inoceramidae Giebel, 1852

Genus *Mytiloides* Brongniart, 1822

Type species: *Ostracites labiatus* Schlotheim (1813, p. 93), by monotypy.

Remarks: According to Harries *et al.* (1996), *Mytiloides* Brongniart, 1822 differs from *Inoceramus* Sowerby, 1814 in its strongly prosocline form, low shell inflation, subequivalve shells lacking strong radial sulci and folds, very thin nacreous and prismatic shell layers (especially in the hinge and umbonal areas), and a weak byssal slit or none at all. They also suggested that the species of

Fig. 2: Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section, southwest Wadi Araba, northern slope of the southern Galala Plateau, showing different lithologies, collected fauna, and the proposed ammonite biozones; the red asterisk indicates the stratigraphic level of the collected inoceramid bivalves.

Mytiloides Brongniart can be divided into at least two major morphologic groups of potential subgeneric rank: (a) *Mytiloides s.s.* consisting of mytiloid-shaped, strongly prosocline taxa (e.g., *M. mytiloides*, *M. labiatus*, *M. striatconcentricus* lineages) and (b) rounded to ovate suberect *Mytiloides* such as *M. "latus"* (sensu Woods, 1912, fig. 41).

***Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz, 1930)**

Fig. 4B

1928. *Inoceramus plicatus* d'Orbigny. – Heinz, p. 63, pl. 4, fig. 4.
 1930. *Inoceramus naumanni* Yok. var. *Kossmati* Heinz. – Heinz in Besaire, pp. 94 and 121.
 1932. *Striatoceramus kossmati* Heinz. – Heinz, p. 4.
 1933. *Striatoceramus kossmati* Heinz. – Heinz, p. 247, pl. 18, fig. 4.
 1935. *Orpheoceramus columbianus* n.sp. – Heinz, p. 304.
 1992. *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). – Walaszczyk, p. 38, pl. 1, figs 1-9. (see additional synonymy)
 2000. *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). – Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.*, p. 322, pl. 9, figs 4-9.
 2008. *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). – Ifrim & Stinnesbeck, p. 949, fig. 8b, c.
 2009. *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). – Nagm, p. 38, text-fig. 4.1D.
 2015. *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). – Nagm, p. 38, fig. 8A.

Material: One almost complete right valve (Kh/Bi-178) from the Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section (bed no. Kh 15). The specimen was collected from the *Vacoceras properium* Total Range Zone.

Measurements in mm: cf. Tab. 1

Description: The studied specimen is medium-sized flat *Mytiloides*, longitudinal obliquely ovate in shell outline (length to height ratio equals 0.78) with a weakly inclined growth axis. The posterior auricle is undeveloped. Anterior and ventral margins almost convex, posterior margin straight to weakly rounded. The straight hinge line accounts for approximately 49% of the shell length. The umbonal ornamentation consists of slightly asymmetrical

closely spaced concentric growth lines. The rest of the shell is characterized by rounded, uniformly spaced rugae. The double-ridged rugae are well developed only in the axial region of the disc, progressively diminishing towards the posterior and anterior margins.

Remarks: *Mytiloides kossmati* can be easily distinguished by its weakly developed posterior auricle, the flat form of subquadrate to subrounded shell outline, weakly inflated disc with maximum inflation in the umbonal part, ornamentation in the form of concentric rings which doubled at the crests of the raised concentric ribs, and cross them obliquely, particularly at the anterior side of the disc (Walaszczyk, 1992; Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000). Walaszczyk (1992), in his full discussion of the Upper Cretaceous Genus *Mytiloides* Brongniart, concluded that *Mytiloides opalensis* (sensu Seitz non Boese, 1934), *Mytiloides goppelnensis* (Badillet & Sornay, 1980) and *Mytiloides modeliaensis* (Sornay, 1981) are synonymous with *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz). Following the interpretations of Kennedy *et al.* (1987, 1989), he also believed that *Mytiloides columbianus* (Heinz, 1935) was quite similar to *Mytiloides kossmati*. Walaszczyk & Cobban (in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000) pointed out that *Mytiloides goppelnensis* (= *Mytiloides opalensis*) differs from *Mytiloides kossmati* in the lack of double-ridged rugae. Therefore, they concluded that *Mytiloides goppelnensis* is the correct name for *Mytiloides opalensis*, and *Mytiloides kossmati* should be used for double-ridged specimens, which have previously been referred to as *Mytiloides columbianus* or *Mytiloides duplicostatus* (Anderson, 1958). With the same conclusion, Ifrim & Stinnesbeck (2008) noted that *Mytiloides kossmati* is similar to *Mytiloides goppelnensis* in terms of ornamentation and shell outline, although the latter species lacks double-ridged rugae.

The general shell form and the ribbing pattern of the studied specimen from Wadi Araba are closely resembles *Mytiloides kossmati* figured in Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.* 2000 (pl. 9, figs 4-9).

Age and geographic distribution: This species was previously recorded from the lower Turonian of Egypt

Table 1: *Mytiloides kossmati* measurements

Specimen No	h	L	H	L	S	l/h	L/H	S/L	α	δ	t	BH
Kh/Bi-178	30.2	24.5	32.5	25.5	12	0.81	0.78	0.47	87°	56°	111°	1.7

Fig. 3: Field photographs showing the different rock units cropping out in the studied section. A: panoramic view of the Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section; B: highly ferruginous, coarse-grained sandstones of the basal part of the pre-Cenomanian Malha Formation; C: reddish-brown cross-bedded sandstone, Malha Formation; D: greenish, fine-grained shaley marl bed with oysters representing the basal part of the Galala Formation; E: close up view of *Pterocera incerta* (d'Orbigny, 1842), embedded in the greenish marl bed, upper Cenomanian, Galala Formation; F: relatively complete, large-sized internal mold of lower Turonian *Choffaticeras* (*Choffaticeras*) *segne* (Solger, 1903), Maghra El Hadida Formation; G: large-sized *Choffaticeras* spp., collected from the lower Turonian "Choffaticeras bed", Maghra El Hadida Formation.

Fig 4: Terminology and measurements of inoceramid bivalve external morphologic features (based on Harries *et al.*, 1996; Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000; Ifrim & Stinnesbeck, 2008).

by Nagm (2009, 2015) and El-Sabbagh *et al.* (2021). *Mytiloides kossmati* is a well-known inoceramid bivalve characterizing the lower Turonian of South America (Colombia), Europe (England, France, Germany, Spain, Poland, Czech Republic, Ukraine), Asia (Japan, Kazakhstan), and Madagascar (Walaszczyk & Cobban, in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000), Brazil (Andrade, 2005), and Mexico (Ifrim & Stinnesbeck, 2008).

Mytiloides puebloensis Walaszczyk & Cobban, in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000

Fig. 4C

2000. *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban, in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000, p. 321, pl. 6, figs 1-11; pl. 7, figs 2-3, 5-8, 12-15, pl. 8, figs 1-11, 13; pl. 10, figs 1, 4, 6-8 (with full synonymy)
2005. *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban. – Gale *et al.*, fig. 16a-b, ?c, f, i, l-m.
2008. *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban. – Ifrim & Stinnesbeck, p. 949, figs 4a, b, 7b.
2018. *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban. – Košťák *et al.*, p. 6, fig. 5G.
2020. *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban. – Košťák *et al.*, p. 166, fig. 8K-L.
2020. *Mytiloides cf. puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban. – Wilmsen *et al.*, p. 14, fig. 8B.

Material: A single left valve, nearly complete (Kh/Bi-181), from the Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section (bed no. Kh 15). The specimen recovered co-occurred with *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz) and is from the *Vacoceras properium* Total Range Zone.

Measurements in mm: cf. Tab. 2

Description: Medium-sized *Mytiloides*, shell outline is subquadrate (length to height ratio equals 0.96) and inequilateral. Shell is weakly inflated, with dorsal maximum inflation. The growth axis is straight to slightly anteriorly convex. Hinge line straight and representing 52% of the shell length. The anterior margin is fairly extended and convex, leading to a ventral margin that is narrowly rounded. The posterior border, which has been partially preserved, is slightly convex. The ornamentation consists of regularly spaced, round-topped asymmetric rugae that are covered with raised growth lines.

Remarks: *Mytiloides puebloensis* was first described as new species and discussed by Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.* (2000), based on material from the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary interval of the U.S. Western Interior. They considered *M. puebloensis* as an evolutionary descendent of *Mytiloides hattini* Elder, 1991. This species is distinguished by its small – to medium – sized shell, with regularly spaced, round topped rugae, covered with regular, raised growth lines, the disc oval in outline to subquadrate, weakly inflated, with dorsal maximum inflation, hinge-line relatively short and straight. According to Ifrim & Stinnesbeck (2008), *Mytiloides puebloensis* has an outline similar to *Mytiloides kossmati* and *Mytiloides goppelnensis*, but it has microrugae throughout the juvenile growth stages, whereas rugae are present throughout ontogeny and become irregular during the adult growth stage. Košťák *et al.* (2018) stated that *Mytiloides puebloensis* differs from *Mytiloides kossmati* by the absence of double-ridged rugae. Moreover, *Mytiloides mytiloides* (Mantell, 1822) differs from the present species in its much lower l/h values, the less regular ornament, and the lower anterior hinge angle values. Furthermore, it has a wide and well-developed posterior auricle.

This is the first record of *Mytiloides puebloensis* from Egypt and North Africa as well. The single specimen from Wadi Araba closely resembles those figured in Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.* (2000, pl. 7, figs 5-8) from the Western Interior, USA, and is very similar to the specimen described and illustrated in Wilmsen *et al.* (2020, fig. 8b) from central Iran.

Age and geographic distribution: According to

Table 2: *Mytiloides puebloensis* measurements

Specimen No	h	L	H	L	S	l/h	L/H	S/L	α	Δ	τ	BH
Kh/Bi-181	32.8	29.4	34.3	33.1	17.3	0.9	0.96	0.52	83°	52°	116°	3.2

Walaszczyk & Cobban in Kennedy *et al.* (2000), *Mytiloides puebloensis* is described from the lowermost Turonian of Colorado, where it co-occurs with *Mytiloides goppelnensis* and *Mytiloides kossmati*. Other records are from the early Turonian of Texas, Portugal, Spain, Kazakhstan (Kennedy *et al.*, 2000), England (Gale *et al.*, 2005), Czech Republic (Košťák *et al.*, 2018, 2020) and possibly Central Iran (Wilmsen *et al.*, 2020).

5. LOWER TURONIAN BIOSTRATIGRAPHY OF WADI ARABA

Based on the occurrence of the Cenomanian ammonoids, three ammonite biozones are well defined in the upper Cenomanian Galala Formation at Wadi Umm Khayshar. They are from base to top: *Neolobites vibrayanus* Total Range Zone (from bed 8 to bed 11), *Vascoceras gamai* Total Range Zone (bed 12), and *Vascoceras cauvini* Total Range Zone (bed 13; see Fig. 2). The last occurrence (LO) of the zonal marker species *Vascoceras cauvini* Chudeau characterizes the uppermost Cenomanian in the study area. The typical upper Cenomanian, highly fossiliferous, greenish fine-grained shaley marl beds containing these ammonoids are overlain by a thickly bedded, reddish fine-grained sandstone (bed 14), which marks the topmost part of the upper Cenomanian Galala Formation and identifies the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the Wadi Umm Khayshar stratigraphic section. Indeed, the uppermost part of these sandstones and the FO of *Vascoceras proprium* in Wadi Araba marks the base of the Turonian and the basal part of Maghra El Hadiad Formation (Fig. 2). Unfortunately, no upper Cenomanian inoceramid bivalves were recorded in the studied section. On the other hand, two inoceramid bivalves have been identified from the lower Turonian of Wadi Umm Khayshar are *Mytiloides kossmati* and *Mytiloides puebloensis*.

Vascoceras proprium Total Range Zone

The *Vascoceras proprium* Zone is defined by the total range of *Vascoceras proprium* (Reyment). This zone is used as a marker biozone to identify the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary and defines the base of the Turonian of the Maghra El Hadida Formation. In the Wadi Umm Khayshar section, the base of the *Vascoceras proprium* Zone is defined by the first appearance datum (FAD; 82 m level) and its upper boundary by the last appearance datum (LAD; 85 m level) of *Vascoceras proprium* (Fig. 2). The zonal marker species, in the study area, is co-occurring with the lower Turonian inoceramid bivalves *Mytiloides kossmati* and *Mytiloides puebloensis*. The associated benthic macrofauna (see Figs 5, 6) includes the bivalves *Plicatula ferryi* Coquand, 1862, *Granocardium productum* (Sowerby, 1832), and *Protocardia hillana* (Sowerby, 1813); the gastropods *Ampulina* sp., and *Tylostoma cossoni* Thomas & Peron, 1889; as well as

the echinoids *Mecaster batnensis* (Coquand, 1962) and *Mecaster turoensis* (Fourtau, 1921).

In the framework of lower Turonian ammonite biostratigraphy of Egypt, the *Vascoceras proprium* Total Range Zone from Wadi Umm Khayshar is equivalent to *Vascoceras durandi* Zone of Luger & Gröschke (1989), the *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone of Kassab (1991), the *Vascoceras proprium*–*Vascoceras ptioti* Zone of Hewaidy *et al.* (2003), the *Vascoceras proprium* Zone of Nagm *et al.* (2010b), Hewaidy *et al.* (2012), and Nagm (2015) from the north Eastern Desert, the *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone of Aly & Abdel-Gawad (2001), as well as *Vascoceras proprium* Zone of Kassab & Obaidalla (2001), El Hedeny (2002), and El-Sabbagh *et al.* (2011) from Sinai.

6. BIOSTRATIGRAPHIC CORRELATION

The inoceramid biostratigraphy of the Cenomanian–Turonian transition has been fully discussed by Walaszczyk & Cobban (in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000) based on the Pueblo, Colorado, section. Inoceramids, according to common consensus, are potentially good index fossils. Many inoceramid species are agreed to be useful for Cretaceous biostratigraphy and may even play a crucial role in layers where ammonoids and other diagnostic groups are scarce. Dhondt (1992) mentioned that the Cenomanian–Turonian transition has traditionally been recognized by the appearance of a group of flattened, elongate inoceramids, previously known as the *Inoceramus labiatus* group (after *Inoceramus labiatus*), and currently as the *Mytiloides* group *sensu lato*. In general, the Cenomanian genus *Inoceramus* Sowerby was replaced by *Mytiloides* Brongniart in the early Turonian. The lower Turonian *Mytiloides* Brongniart is distinguished from the Cenomanian *Inoceramus* Sowerby by its shell outline (labiatoid), weaker inflation, and ornamentation. The base of the Turonian was established by Kennedy *et al.* (1987) and Hancock (1991) to be at the base of *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* assemblage Zone, which co-occurred with *Vascoceras proprium*, that is possibly more widespread regionally than the index-species. Birkelund *et al.* (1984) proposed that instead of using the zonal index *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* as marker species for the basal Turonian, it may be better to use the appearance of a vascoceratid, possibly *Vascoceras proprium*. Elder (1991) and Bengtson *et al.* (1996) proposed the first appearance of *Mytiloides hattini* and *Mytiloides wiedmanni* (Lopez, 1992) as markers for the basal Turonian. According to Hancock (1991), the first appearance of the inoceramid bivalve *Mytiloides columbianus*, which is often the first abundant *Mytiloides* in the lower Turonian, marks the base of the *flexuosum* Zone. According to Kennedy *et al.* (1987, 1989), the *Mytiloides columbianus* is considered a synonym of *Mytiloides kossmati*. Birkelund *et al.* (1984) suggested

Fig. 5: A: *Vascoceras proprium* (Reyment, 1954). A1: side view; A2: ventral view; AUGDM/Kh/Amm-50 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). B: *Mytiloides kossmati* (Heinz, 1930), external view of right valve; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-178 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). C: *Mytiloides puebloensis* Walaszczyk & Cobban, in Kennedy *et al.*, 2000, external view of left valve; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-181 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). D, E: *Plicatula ferryi* Coquand, 1862 articulated specimens; D: external view of left valve; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-161; E1: external view of right valve; E2: external view of left valve; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-77. F: *Granocardium productum* (Sowerby, 1832) articulated specimen; F1: external view of right valve; F2: dorsal view; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-76 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). All specimens from Maghra El Hadida Formation, lower Turonian. Bar Scale = 20 mm.

Fig. 6: A, *Protocardia hillana* (Sowerby, 1813), articulated specimen; A1: external view of right valve; A2: dorsal view; AUGDM/Kh/Bi-150 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). B: *Ampullina* sp.; B1: side view; B2: apertural view; AUGDM/Kh/Ga-23 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). C: *Tylostoma (Tylostoma) cossoni* Thomas & Peron, 1889. C1: apertural view; C2: apical view; AUGDM/Kh/Ga-09 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). D: *Hemiaster (Mecaster) batnensis* Coquand, 1862. D1: adapical view; D2: side view; AUGDM/Kh/Ech-45. E-F: *Hemiaster (Mecaster) heberti* (Coquand, 1862). E1: adapical view; E2: adoral view; AUGDM/Kh/Ech-48. F1: adapical view; F2: adoral view; F3: side view; AUGDM/Kh/Ech-51. All specimens from Maghra El Hadida Formation, lower Turonian. Bar Scale = 20 mm.

Fig. 7: *Choffaticeras* (*Leoniceras*) *luciae* (Pervinquière, 1907) from the lower Turonian Maghra El Hadida Formation (above the *Vascoceras proprium* Zone). A: side view, x1; AUGDM/Kh/Amm-37; B: side view, x1; AUGDM/Kh/Amm-23. Bar Scale = 30 mm.

Fig. 8: *Choffaticeras* (*Choffaticeras*) *segne* (Solger, 1903) from the lower Turonian Maghra El Hadida Formation (above the *Vascoceras proprium* Zone). A1: side view, x1; A2: ventral view; AUGDM/Kh/Amm-22 (after Aly *et al.*, 2023). Bar Scale = 30 mm.

that a widespread flood of *Mytiloides* could be correlated to the base of the early Turonian *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone. Walaszczyk *et al.* (1992) agreed that the lower part of the *M. kossmati* Zone corresponds to the *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone in ammonite terms. Kennedy *et al.* (2000) proposed *Mytiloides kossmati* as a stratigraphic marker based on its occurrence in the GSSP. The Turonian base, according to current consensus, is at the lowest occurrence of the ammonite *Watinoceras devonense* Wright & Kennedy, 1981 (Kennedy *et al.*, 2000), with the GSSP located in Pueblo, Colorado, USA. This level corresponds to the first occurrence of *Mytiloides puebloensis*, and the base of the *puebloensis* Zone (see Table 3). Gale *et al.* (2005) placed the base of the Turonian at the last occurrences of late Cenomanian inoceramid bivalves *Inoceramus pictus* and the first occurrence of the early Turonian *Watinoceras devonense* and *Mytiloides puebloensis*.

Therefore, *Vascoceras proprium* Total Range Zone of Wadi Araba is equivalent to the *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone of Robaszynski *et al.* (1990), Chancellor *et al.* (1994) and Abdallah *et al.* (2000) from Tunisia; the *Watinoceras* sp.–*Vascoceras proprium* Zone and

Vascoceras durandi–*Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone of Charriere *et al.* (1998) and Lehmann & Herbig (2009) from Morocco; the *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* Zone of Hancock *et al.* (1993) from the North America; the *Watinoceras devonense* Zone of Amédro *et al.* (2020) from France; the lower part of *Watinoceras coloradoense* Zone of Kennedy (1984) from Western Europe. This zone corresponds to *Watinoceras devonense* and *Pseudaspidoceras flexuosum* zones from the Western Interior of United States and the *Watinoceras devonense* Zone from Tethyan region, according to the Standard Ammonite Zonation (Gale *et al.*, 2020). In addition, it is equivalent to *Vascoceras proprium* Zone of Aly *et al.* (2008) and Nagm *et al.* (2017) from Jordan; as well as the *Vascoceras ptioti* Zone of Lewy *et al.* (1984) from Israel.

7. INOCERAMID PALAEOBIOGEOGRAPHY

Paleobiogeographically, it is widely known that inoceramid bivalves reached their evolutionary peak during the Late Cretaceous (Dhondt, 1992). Indeed, most of the Late Cretaceous and during the Cenomanian–Turonian,

Table 3: Correlation between the proposed upper Cenomanian–lower Turonian Tethyan and North American ammonite and inoceramid zones and the established zones in the current work.

Substage	Ammonite Biozones (Gradstein <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Gale <i>et al.</i> , 2020)		Inoceramid Bivalve Biozones		Present Work Wadi Araba Egypt
	Tethyan	Western Interior, North America	Kennedy <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Walaszczyk <i>et al.</i> (2013)	
Lower Turonian	<i>Mammites nodosoides</i>	<i>Mammites nodosoides</i>	<i>Mytiloides Mytiloides</i>	<i>Mytiloides mytiloides</i>	<i>Wrightoceras muniri</i>
	<i>Watinoceras coloradoense</i> / <i>Watinoceras devonense</i>	<i>Vascoceras birchbyi</i> <i>Pseudaspido. flexuosum</i> <i>Watinoceras devonense</i>			<i>Mytiloides kossmati</i>
			<i>Mytiloides puebloensis</i>	<i>Mytiloides puebloensis</i>	<i>Vascoceras proprium</i>
Upper Cenomanian	<i>Neocardioceras judii</i>	<i>Nigericeras scotti</i> to <i>Conlinoceras tarrantense</i> (15 zones)	<i>Mytiloides hattani</i>	<i>Mytiloides hattani</i>	<i>Vascoceras cauvini</i>
	<i>Metoicoceras geslinianum</i>		<i>Inoceramus pictus</i>	<i>Inoceramus pictus</i>	<i>Vascoceras gamai</i>
	<i>Calycoceras naviculare</i>				<i>Neolobites vibrayeanus</i>

Early Turonian

Fig. 9: Paleogeographic distribution of *Mytiloides* Brongniart, 1822; data based on Walaszczyk (1992), Harries *et al.* (1996), Kennedy *et al.* (2000), Ifrim & Stinnesbeck (2008), Tröger (2009). Map modified after Scotese (2014).

inoceramids were cosmopolitan in distribution. Harries *et al.* (1996) reported that the inoceramid species have intercontinental to cosmopolitan distribution in normal marine, temperate zone facies; they are much less common, but still widespread, in the Tethyan Realm. Lower Turonian species from the genus *Mytiloides* have been deemed the most acceptable and useful biostratigraphic elements for the Turonian zonation, along with ammonites, due to their rapid evolution and their broad paleogeographic distribution (see Fig. 9). For *Mytiloides*, Keller (1982) argued that *Mytiloides labiatus* (Schlotheim), *M. mytiloides* (Mantell), *M. submytiloides* (Seitz, 1934), *M. goppelnensis* (Badillet & Sornay), and *M. hercynicus* (Petrascheck, 1903) have a worldwide or nearly worldwide distribution in the lower Turonian. According to Ifrim & Stinnesbeck (2008), the early Turonian *Mytiloides kossmati* could be a useful stratigraphic marker for long-distance correlation. Walaszczyk (1992) and Walaszczyk *et al.* (2013) considered the lower Turonian *Mytiloides labiatus* group: *M. puebloensis*, *M. kossmati* and *M. mytiloides*, with cosmopolitan distribution. According to the current authors' conclusions, which mostly agree with Voigt (1995), the Trans-Shaharian Seaways is thought to have served as a path for ammonites and inoceramids to South America and North Africa during the late Cenomanian to early Turonian.

8. FINAL REMARKS

Mytiloides kossmati and *Mytiloides puebloensis* coincided with *Vascoceras proprium* in the Wadi Umm Khayshar Umm; their occurrences mark the base of the early Turonian in the area under study. In Egypt, inoceramid bivalves are extremely rare in Cenomanian–Turonian strata. Seibertz (1996) concluded that widespread freshwater input, large areas with too shallow water depth (high energy and temperature), large-scaled resedimentation, and strong occupancy of biotopes by many other pelecypods contributed to the general scarcity of inoceramid bivalves in Egypt during the Upper Cretaceous. According to Nagm *et al.* (2011), the generally shallow marine environment and its influence on important environmental factors such as water energy and temperature most likely prevented inoceramid bivalves from occupying the Egyptian (as well as the entire north African) shallow-shelf areas. The abundance of extremely shallow marine environments and high temperatures, together with the richness of shallow marine fauna (such as oysters, rudist bivalves, gastropods, echinoids, the frequent occurrences of corals and sponges), may be the cause of the inoceramid bivalves' scarcity in the Cenomanian–Turonian sequences of Egypt. Paleogeographically, Egyptian Cenomanian–Turonian inoceramid bivalves belong to the Mediterranean bioprovince of the Tethyan

Realm. The inoceramid taxa recognized and described herein from the study area are known from most of the European and US Western Interior sections.

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REFERENCES

- Aal A. A. & Lelek J. J. 1994. Structural development of the northern Sinai, Egypt, and its implication on the hydrocarbon prospectively of the Mesozoic. *In: GEO 94, the Middle East Geosciences Conference Bahrain*, 1: 15-30.
- Abdallah A. M. & Adindani A. 1963. Notes on the Cenomanian – Turonian contact in the Galala Plateau, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Geology*, 7(1): 67-70.
- Abdallah H., Sassi S., Meister C. & Souissi R. 2000. Stratigraphie séquentielle et paléogéographie à la limite Cénomanién Turonien dans la région de Gafsa–Chott area (Tunisie centrale). *Cretaceous Research*, 21: 35-106.
- Abdel-Gawad G. I., El-Sheikh H. A., Abdelhamid M. A., El-Beshtawy M. K., Abed M. M., Fürsich F. T. & El Qot G. M. 2004. Stratigraphic studies on some Upper Cretaceous successions in Sinai, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 4: 263-303.
- Abdel-Gawad G. I., El Qot G. M. & Mekawy M. S. 2006. Cenomanian–Turonian macrobiostratigraphy of Abu Darage area, Northern Galala, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Proceeding of the International Conference on the Geology of the Arab World*, Cairo University, 553-568.
- Abdel-Gawad G. I., El Qot G. M. & Mekawy M. S. 2007. Macrobiostratigraphy of the Upper Cretaceous succession from southern Galala, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Second international Conference of the Tethys*, Cairo University: 329-349.
- Abdelhady A. A., Mohamed O., Hassan A. A. & Mohamed R. M. S. 2021. Cenomanian oyster communities from a tide-dominated epeiric ramp in the southern Tethys: A sediment-fauna relationship. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2021.104306>
- Abd-Elhameed S., Salama Y. & Mahmoud A. 2023. Changes in macrofaunal groups before, during and after the Cenomanian–Turonian biotic crisis in north Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Palaeobiodiversity and Palaeoenvironments*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12549-023-00573-3>
- Abdel-Raheem Kh. M., Ali M. S. M., Azab M. M. & Abdelhady A. A. 2020. Paleocology and paleobiogeography of the Cenomanian–Turonian bivalves from the Southern Galala Plateau (Eastern Desert, Egypt). *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 168: 1-15.
- Aly M. F. & Abdel-Gawad G. I. 2001. Upper Cenomanian – Lower Turonian ammonites from north and central Sinai, Egypt. *El-Minia Science Bulletin* 13(2) -14(1): 17-60.
- Aly M. F., Smadi A. & Abu Azzam H. 2008. Late Cenomanian–Early Turonian ammonites of Jordan. *Revue de Paléobiologie*, 27(1): 43-71.
- Aly M. F., Zidan A. M., Tantawy A., El Soughier M. I. & Bulot L. G. 2023. Late Cenomanian–early Turonian ammonite successions of north Eastern Desert, Egypt: biostratigraphy and paleobiogeographic implications. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 28. doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2023.105095.
- Amédéo F., Robaszynski F., Châtellier H., Ferchaud P. & Matrimon B. 2020. Identification of a *Romaniceras* (*Romaniceras*) *marigniacum* sp. nov. ammonite biohorizon (Middle Turonian) at the base of the Tuffeau Jaune de Touraine (France). *Carnets de Géologie*, 20(4): 37-89.
- Anderson F. M. 1958. Upper Cretaceous of the Pacific Coast. *Memoir of the Geological Society of America*, 71: 378 pp.
- Andrade, E.J. 2005. *Turonian inoceramids and biostratigraphy of the Sergipe Basin, northeastern Brazil: an integrated study of the Votorantim and Nassau quarries*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis; Heidelberg, 155 pp.
- Awad G. H. & Abdalla A. M. 1966. Upper Cretaceous in southern Galala, Eastern Desert with emphasis on neighboring areas. *Egyptian Journal of Geology*, 10(2): 125-144.
- Ayoub-Hannaa W. & Fürsich F. T. 2012a. Cenomanian–Turonian ammonites from eastern Sinai, Egypt and their biostratigraphic significance. *Beringeria* 42: 57-92.
- Ayoub-Hannaa W. & Fürsich F. T. 2012b. Palaeoecology and environmental significance of benthic associations from the Cenomanian–Turonian of eastern Sinai, Egypt. *Beringeria*, 42: 93-138.
- Badillet G. & Sornay J. 1980. Sur quelques formes du groupe d'*Inoceramus labiatus* décrites par O. Seitz. Impossibilité d'utiliser ce groupe pour une datation stratigraphique du Turonien inférieur du Saumurois (France). *Compte Rendu Académie Science Paris, Série D*, 290: 323-325.
- Bengtson P., Cobban W. A., Dodsworth P., Gale A. S., Kennedy W. J., Lamolda M. A., et al. 1996. The Turonian stage and substage boundaries. *Bulletin de l'Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Sciences de la Terre*, 66 (Suppl.): 69-79.
- Besaire H. 1930. Recherches géologiques à Madagascar. Contributions à l'étude des ressources minérales. *Thèses présentées à la Faculté des Sciences de l'Université de Paris*, Toulouse, 172 pp.
- Birkelund T., Hancock J. M., Hart M. B., Rawson P. F., Remane J., Robaszynski F., Schmid F. & Surlyk F. 1984. Cretaceous stage boundaries – Proposals. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 33: 3-20.
- Blankenhorn M. 1900. Neues zur Geologie und Paläontologie Ägyptens. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Geologischen Gesellschaft*, 52: 21-47.
- Brongniart A. in Cuvier G. 1822. Description géologiques des couches des environs de Paris. *In: Les Ossements Fossiles*. Vol. II(2): 229-648.
- Carter J.G., Altaba C.R., Anderson L.C., Araujo R., Biakov A.S., Bogan A.E., Campbell D.C., Campbell M., Chen

- Jin-hua, Cope J.C.W., Delvene G., Dijkstra H.H., Fang Zong-jie & Gardner R. N. *et al.* 2011. A synoptical classification of the Bivalvia (Mollusca). *Paleontological Contributions*, 4: 1-47.
- Chancellor G. R., Kennedy W. J. & Hancock J. M. 1994. Turonian ammonite faunas from central Tunisia. *Special Papers in Palaeontology*, 50: 1-188.
- Charriere A., Andreu B., Cizak R., Kennedy W. J., Rossi A. & Vila J. M. 1998. La transgression du Cénomanién supérieur dans la Haute Moulouya et le Moyen Atlas méridional, Maroc. *Geobios*, 31: 551-569.
- Choffat P. 1898. Recueil d'études paléontologiques sur la faune crétacique du Portugal. Volume 1, Espèces nouvelles ou peu connues. Deuxième série: Les Ammonées du Bellasien, des Couches à *Neolobites Vibrayanus*, du Turonien et du Sénonien. *Direction des Travaux Géologiques du Portugal*, 2: 43-86.
- Chudeau R. 1909. Ammonites du Damergou (Sahara méridional). *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France* 4(9): 67-71, pls 1-3.
- Conoco C. 1987. Geological map of Egypt. *The Egyptian general petroleum corporation*, Cairo.
- Coquand M. H. 1862. Géologie et Paléontologie de la région sud de la Province de Constantine. *Mémoires de la Société d'Emulation de la Provence*, 2: 1-341.
- Courtiller M. A. 1860. Description de trois nouvelles espèces d'ammonites du terrain crétacé des environs du Saumur. *Mémoires de la Société d'Agriculture, Sciences et Arts d'Angers* 3: 246-252, 3 pls.
- Dhondt A. V. 1992. Cretaceous inoceramid biogeography: a review. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 92: 217-232.
- Douvillé M. H. 1928. Les ammonites de la Craie supérieure en Egypte et au Sinai. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences de l'Institut de France*, 60: 1-41.
- El-Akkad S. & Abdallah A. M. 1971. Contribution to geology of Gebel Ataqa area. *Annales of the Geological Survey of Egypt*, 1: 21-42.
- Elder W. P. 1991. *Mytiloides hattini* n.sp.: a guide fossil for the base of the Turonian in the Western Interior of North America. *Journal of Paleontology*, 65: 234-241.
- El Hawat A. 1997. Sedimentary basins of Egyptian: An overview of dynamic stratigraphy. In: Selley R.C. (ed.), *Sedimentary Basins of the World*, Elsevier, 3: 39-85.
- El-Hedeny M. M. 2002. Cenomanian – Coniacian ammonites from the west–central Sinai, Egypt, and their significance in biostratigraphy. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Monatshefte*, 7: 397-425.
- El-Hedeny M. M. & Nafee S. A. 2001. Upper Cenomanian ammonites from Bir Quiseib Northern Galala, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 1: 115-134.
- El Qot G. M. 2006. Late Cretaceous macrofossils from Sinai, Egypt. *Beringeria* 36: 3-163.
- El Qot G. M. 2008. Upper Cenomanian–Lower Santonian ammonites from Galala Plateaux, north Eastern Desert, Egypt: A systematic paleontology. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 8: 247-289.
- El-Sabbagh A., Tantawy A., Keller G., Khozyem H., Spangenberg J., Adatte T. & Gertsch B. 2011. Stratigraphy of the Cenomanian–Turonian Oceanic Anoxic Event OAE2 in shallow shelf sequences of NE Egypt. *Cretaceous Research* 32: 705-722.
- El-Sabbagh A. M., Nagm E., Mansour A. S., El-Hedeny M. M., Abdelaal A. A., Mansour H. N. & Rashwan M. A. 2021. Palaeoecological and palaeoenvironmental analyses of Cenomanian–early Turonian macrobenthic faunas from the northern Eastern Desert of Egypt. *Cretaceous Research*, 125: 1-30.
- Fourtau R. 1921. Catalogue des invertébrés fossiles de l'Égypte. Terrains Crétacés, 3, Echinodermes (supplément). Geological Survey of Egypt, Paleontological Series 5: 101 pp.
- Gale A. S., Kennedy W. J., Voigt S. & Walaszczyk I. 2005. Stratigraphy of the Upper Cenomanian–Lower Turonian Chalk succession at Eastbourne, Sussex, UK: ammonites, inoceramid bivalves and stable carbon isotopes. *Cretaceous Research*, 26 (3): 460-487.
- Gale A. S., Mutterlose J., Batenburg S., Gradstein F. M., Agterberg F. P., Ogg J. G. & Petrizzo M. R. 2020. Chapter 27 – The Cretaceous Period. In: Gradstein F. M., Ogg J. G., Schmitz M. D. & Ogg G. M. (Eds), *Geologic Time Scale*, Elsevier: 1023-1086.
- Gradstein F. M., Ogg J. G. & Smith A. G. 2004. *A geologic time scale*. University Press, Cambridge, 589 pp.
- Giebel C. G. A. 1852. Deutschlands Petrefakten. Ein systematisches Verzeichnis aller in Deutschland und den Angrenzenden Laendern Vorkommenden Petrefakten Nebst Angabe der Synonymen und Fundorte. A. Abel, Leipzig: 329-441.
- Hancock J. M. 1991. Ammonite scales for the Cretaceous system. *Cretaceous Research*, 12: 259-191.
- Hancock J. M., Kennedy W. J. & Cobban W. A. 1993. A Correlation of the Upper Albian to basal Coniacian sequences of north-west Europe, Texas and the United States Western Interior. In: Caldwell W. G. E. & Kauffman E. G. (eds), The evolution of the western interior foreland basin. *Geological Association of Canada Special Paper*, 39: 453-476.
- Harries P. J., Kauffman E. G. & Crampton J. S. (Redactors). 1996. Lower Turonian Euramerican Inoceramidae: a morphologic, taxonomic, and biostratigraphic overview. A report from the First Workshop on Early Turonian Inoceramids (Oct. 5-8, 1992) in Hamburg, Germany; organized by Heinz Hilbrecht and Peter Harries. *Mitteilungen aus dem Geologisch-Paläontologischen Institut der Universität Hamburg*, 77: 641-671.
- Heinz R. 1928. Über die Oberkreide-Inoceramen Süd-Amerikas und ihre Beziehungen zu denen Europas und anderer Gebiete. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der oberkretazischen Inoceramen V. *Mitteilungen aus dem Mineralogisch-Geologischen Staatsinstitut, Hamburg*, 10: 42-97.
- Heinz R. in Besairie H. 1930. *Recherches géologiques à Madagascar. Contribution à l'étude des ressources minérales*. Thèses présentées à la Faculté des Sciences de l'Université de Paris: 272 pp.
- Heinz R. 1930. Zur stratigraphischen Stellung der Sonnenbergsschichten bei Waltersdorf i Sa. (west-südwestlich von Zittau). Beiträge zur Kenntnis der oberkretazischen Inoceramen IX. *Jahresbericht des Niedersächsischen geologischen Vereins zu Hannover*, 23: 23-29.
- Heinz R. 1932. Sur les Inocérames de Madagascar. Leur relations avec les Inocérames d'Europe et d'autres régions et leur importance pour l'étude stratigraphique du Crétacé. Contribution à la connaissance des Inocérames XIII. Gouvernement Général de Madagascar et Dépendances.

- Annales Géologiques du Service des Mines*, Tananarive, 2: 3-7.
- Heinz R. 1933. Inoceramen von Madagascar und ihre Bedeutung für die Kreide-Stratigraphie. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Geologischen Gesellschaft*, Berlin, 85: 241-259.
- Heinz R. 1935. Unterkreide-Inoceramen von der Kapverden-Insel Maio. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Inoceramen XVIII. *Neues Jahrbuch für Mineralogie und Geologie, Beilage-Band 73*, Abteilung B, Berlin, 302-311.
- Heinz R. 1936. Inoceramidos de Alicante, Valencia y Baleares (Inoceramen 15). *Boletín de la Sociedad Española de Historia Natural* Madrid, 36: 91-99.
- Hewaidy A. A., Azab M. M. & Farouk S. 2003. Ammonite biostratigraphy of the upper Cretaceous succession in the area West of Wadi Araba, North Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 3: 331-359.
- Hewaidy A. A., Awad M. H., Farouk S. & El Balkeimy A. 2012. Cenomanian Biostratigraphy and sequence stratigraphy of southern Galala plateau, north Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 12: 143-172.
- Ifrim C. & Stinnesbeck W. 2008. Cenomanian–Turonian high-resolution biostratigraphy of north-eastern Mexico and its correlation with the GSSP and Europe. *Cretaceous Research*, 29: 943-956.
- Issawi B., El Hinnawi M., Francis M. & Mazhar A. 1999. The Phanerozoic geology of Egypt. The Egyptian geological survey, special publication, 76: 1-462.
- Kassab A. 1985. *Paleontological and stratigraphical studies of Cretaceous sections in Wadi Qena and Wadi Tarfa, Eastern Desert, Egypt*. Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Egypt, 221 pp.
- Kassab A. S. 1991. Cenomanian – Coniacian biostratigraphy of the northern Eastern Desert, Egypt, based on ammonites. *Newsletters on Stratigraphy*, 25: 25-35.
- Kassab A. S. 1994. Upper Cretaceous ammonites from the El Sheikh Fadl-Rad Gharib Road, Northeastern Desert, Egypt. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen H.*, 2: 108-128.
- Kassab A. S. 1996. Cenomanian – Turonian boundary in the Gulf of Suez region, Egypt: towards an inter-regional correlation, based on ammonites. *Geological Society of Egypt, Special Publication*, 2: 61-98.
- Kassab A. S. & Obaidalla N. A. 2001. Integrated biostratigraphy and inter-regional correlation of the Cenomanian–Turonian deposits of Wadi Feiran, Sinai, Egypt. *Cretaceous Research*, 22: 105-114.
- Keller S. 1982. Die Oberkreide der Sack-Mulde bei Alfeld (Cenoman Unter-Coniac). Lithologie, Biostratigraphie und Inoceramen. *Geologisches Jahrbuch, Reihe A*, 64: 3-171.
- Kennedy W. J. 1984. Ammonite faunas and the “standard zones” of the Cenomanian to Maastrichtian Stages in their type areas, with some proposals for the definition of the stage boundaries by ammonites. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 33: 147-161.
- Kennedy W. J., Wright C.W. & Hancock J. M. 1987. Basal Turonian ammonites from west Texas. *Palaeontology*, 30: 27-74.
- Kennedy W. J., Cobban W. A., Hancock J. M. & Hook S. C. 1989. Biostratigraphy of the Chispa Summit Formation at its type locality: a Cenomanian through Turonian reference section for Trans–Pecos Texas. *Bulletin of the Geological Institution of the University of Upsala*, N.S., 15: 39-119.
- Kennedy W. J., Walaszczyk I. & Cobban W. A. 2000. Pueblo, Colorado, USA, candidate Global Boundary Stratotype Section and Point for the base of the Turonian Stage of the Cretaceous, and for the base of the Middle Turonian Substage, with a revision of the Inoceramidae. *Acta Geologica Polonica*, 50: 295-334.
- Kora M., Khalil H. & Sobhy M. 2001. Stratigraphy and microfacies of some Cenomanian – Turonian succession in the Gulf of Suez region, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Geology*, 45(1): 413-4439.
- Košťák M., Čech S., Uličný D., Sklenář J., Ekrť B. & Mazuch M. 2018. Ammonites, inoceramids and stable carbon isotopes of the Cenomanian-Turonian OAE2 interval in central Europe: Pecínov quarry, Bohemian Cretaceous Basin (Czech Republic). *Cretaceous Research*, 87: 150-173.
- Košťák M., Kohout O., Mazuch M. & Čech S. 2020. An unusual occurrence of vascoceratid ammonites in the Bohemian Cretaceous Basin (Czech Republic) marks the lower Turonian boundary between the Boreal and Tethyan realms in central Europe. *Cretaceous Research*, 108: 1-11.
- Kuss J., Scheibner C. & Gietl R. 2000. Carbonate platform to basin transition along an Upper Cretaceous to Lower Tertiary Syrian Arc Uplift, Galala Plateaus, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *GeoArabia*, 5(3): 405-424.
- Lehmann J. & Herbig H. G. 2009. Late Cretaceous ammonites from the Bou Angueur syncline (Middle Atlas, Morocco) – stratigraphic and palaeobiogeographic implications. *Palaeontographica A*, 289: 45-87.
- Lewy Z., Kennedy W. J. & Chancellor G. E. 1984. Co-occurrence of *Metoicoceras geslinianum* (d’Orbigny) and *Vascoceras cauvini* Chudeau (Cretaceous Ammonoidea) in the southern Negev (Israel) and its stratigraphic implications. *Newsletters on Stratigraphy*, 13: 67-76.
- Lopez G. 1992. Paleontología y Bioestratigrafía de los inocerámidos (Bivalvia) del Cretácico superior de la Cuenca Navarro-Cántabra y de la Plataforma Norcastellana. Parte II: Estudio sistemático de los subgéneros *Mytiloides* Brongniart y *Magadiceramus* Seitz. *Boletín Geológico y Minero*, 103(3): 70-135.
- Luger P. & Gröschke M. 1989. Late Cretaceous ammonites from the Wadi Qena area in the Egyptian Eastern Desert. *Palaeontology* 32(2): 355-407.
- Mantell G. A. 1822. *The fossils of the South Downs, or illustrations of the geology of Sussex*. Lupton Relfe, London, 328 pp.
- Mekawy M. S. 2007. Upper Cretaceous bivalves from Galala Plateaux, North eastern desert, Egypt: a systematic Paleontology. *Egyptian Journal of Paleontology*, 7: 197-243.
- Meneisy M. Y. 1990. Vulcanicity. In: Said R. (ed.), *The Geology of Egypt*. Balkema, Rotterdam: 157-184.
- Moneer E. M. 2015. *Macropaleontology Studies on the Upper Cretaceous (Cenomanian–Turonian) Fauna in Northern Eastern Desert, Egypt*. M.Sc Thesis, Al-Azhar University, Egypt, 343 pp.
- Nagm E. 2009. *Integrated Stratigraphy, Palaeontology and Facies Analysis of the Cenomanian–Turonian (Upper Cretaceous) Galala and Maghra El Hadida Formations of the Western Wadi Araba, Eastern Desert, Egypt*. PhD thesis, Würzburg University: 213 pp.
- Nagm E. 2015. Stratigraphic significance of rapid faunal change across the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Cretaceous Research*, 52: 9-24.

- Nagm E. & Wilmsen M. 2012. Late Cenomanian–Turonian (Cretaceous) ammonites from Wadi Qena, central Eastern Desert, Egypt: taxonomy, biostratigraphy and palaeobiogeographic implications. *Acta Geologica Polonica*, 62(1): 63-89.
- Nagm E., Wilmsen M., Aly M. F. & Hewaidy A. 2010a. Upper Cenomanian–Turonian (Upper Cretaceous) ammonoids from the western Wadi Araba, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Cretaceous Research*, 31: 473-499.
- Nagm E., Wilmsen M., Aly M. F. & Hewaidy A. 2010b. Biostratigraphy of the Upper Cenomanian–Turonian (lower Upper Cretaceous) successions of the western Wadi Araba, Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Newsletters on Stratigraphy*, 44(1): 17-35.
- Nagm E., Wilmsen M., Čec, S., Wood, C. J. 2011. An inoceramid bivalve tentatively assigned to the group of *Inoceramus pictus* from the Upper Cenomanian of Egypt (Galala Formation, Wadi Qena, central Eastern Desert). *Freiberger Forschungshefte*, C540: 91-102.
- Nagm E., Farouk S. & Ahmad F. 2017. The Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in Jordan: ammonite biostratigraphy and faunal turnover. *Geobios* 50: 37-47.
- Nagm E., Farouk S., Ahmad F. & Elamri Z. 2019. Ammonite zonal scheme for the upper Cenomanian of the southern Tethys margin from Jordan to Tunisia, with palaeobiogeographic implications. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 160: 103-641.
- Orbigny A. d'. 1840-1842. *Paléontologie Française. Terrains Crétacés*: 1. Céphalopodes: 1-120 (1840), 121-430 (1841), and 431-662 (1842).
- Parkinson J. 1819. Remarks on the fossils collected by Mr. Phillips near Dover and Folkestone. *Transactions of the Geological Society of London*, 5: 52-59.
- Peron A. 1897. Les ammonites du Crétacé supérieur de l'Algérie. *Mémoires de la Société Géologique de France*, 7: 25-88.
- Pervinquier L. 1907. Etudes de Paléontologie tunisienne. 1. Céphalopodes des Terrains secondaires. *Carte géologique de la Tunisie*: 1-438.
- Petrascheck W. 1903. Ueber Inoceramen aus der Kreide Böhmens und Sachsens. *Jahresberichte der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Geologischen Reichsanstalt*, 53(1), 153-168.
- Reyment R. A. 1954. Some new Upper Cretaceous ammonites from Nigeria. *Colonial Geology and Mineral Resources*, 4: 248-270, pls 1-5.
- Robaszynski F., Caron M., Dupuis C., Amédro F., González Donoso J. M., Linares D., Hardenbol J., Gartner S., Calandra F. & Deloffre R. 1990. A tentative integrated stratigraphy in the Turonian of central Tunisia: formations, zones and sequential stratigraphy in the Kalaat Senan area. *Bulletin des Centres de Recherches Exploration-Production, Elf-Aquitaine*, 14(1): 213-384.
- Rosenthal E., Weinberger G., Almogi-Labin A. & Flexer A. 2000. Late Cretaceous–Early Tertiary Development of Depositional Basins in Samaria as a Reflection of Eastern Mediterranean Tectonic Evolution. *American Association of Petroleum Geologists Bulletin*, 84(7): 997-1014.
- Said R. 1990. *The Geology of Egypt*. Balkema, Rotterdam, 721 pp.
- Seibertz E. 1996. Endemic and cosmopolitan *Inoceramus* species from Egyptian Upper Cretaceous trans- and regression cycles. *Mitteilungen aus dem Geologisch-Paläontologischen Institut der Universität Hamburg*, 77: 315-335.
- Seitz O. 1934. Die Variabilität des *Inoceramus labiatus* v. Schloth. *Jahrbuch der Preußischen Geologischen Landesamt*, 55: 429-474.
- Schlotheim E. F. von. 1813. Beiträge zur Naturgeschichte der Versteinerungen in geognostischer Hinsicht. *Taschenbuch für die gesammte Mineralogie, mit Hinsicht auf die neuesten Entdeckungen, herausgegeben von Dr. Carl Caesar Leonhard*, 7: 3-134.
- Scotese C. R. 2014. *Atlas of Late Cretaceous Maps, PALEOMAP Atlas for ArcGIS*, volume 2, The Cretaceous, Maps 16-22, Mollweide Projection, PALEOMAP Project, Evanston, IL.
- Solger F. 1903. Über die Jugendentwicklung von *Sphenodiscus lenticularis* Owen und seine Beziehungen zur Gruppe der Tissotian. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Geologischen Gesellschaft*, 5: 69-84.
- Sornay J. 1981. Inocérames (Bivalvia) du Turonien Inférieur de Colombie (Amérique du Sud). *Annales de Paléontologie*, 67(2): 135-148.
- Sowerby J. 1812-1822. The Mineral Conchology of Great Britain, or coloured figures and descriptions of those remains of testaceous animals or shells which have been preserved at various times and depths in the earth. *The author, London*. 1812-1815, Vol. 1, vii+ 242 pp., pls 1-102. 1815-1818, Vol. 2, 252 pp., pl. 103-203. 1818-1821, Vol. 3, 194 pp., pls 204-306. 1821-1822, Vol. 4, 1-114, pls 307-383.
- Sowerby J. de C. 1823-1846. The Mineral Conchology of Great Britain, or coloured figures and descriptions of those remains of testaceous animals or shells which have been preserved at various times and depths in the earth. *The author, London*. 1823, Vol. 4, 115-160, pls 384-407. 1823-1825, Vol. 5, 176 pp., pls 408-503. 1826-1829, Vol. 6, 237 pp., pls. 504-609. 1840-1846.
- Thomas P. & Peron A. 1889-1893. Description des mollusques fossiles des Terrains Crétacés de la région sud des Haut-Plateaux de la Tunisie recueillis en 1885 et 1886 par M. Philippe Thomas. *Exploration Scientifique de la Tunisie*: XII+ 1-405, 35 pls (XII+1-103 (1889); 105-327 (1891); 328-405 (1893).
- Thomel G. 1966. Ammonites. In: Porthault B., Thomel G. & Villoutreys O. de (eds), Etude biostratigraphique du Cénomanien du bassin supérieur de l'Esteron (Alpes Maritimes). Le problème de la limite Cénomanien-Turonien dans le sud-est de la France. *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France*, (7^e série), 8: 423-439, pls 8-11.
- Tröger K.-A. 2009. Katalog oberkretazischer Inoceramen. *Geologica Saxonica*, 55: 1-188.
- Voigt S. 1995. Paleobiogeography of early Late Cretaceous inoceramid in the context of a new global paleogeography. *Cretaceous Research*, 16: 343-356.
- Walaszczyk I. 1992. Turonian to Santonian deposits of the Central Polish Uplands; their facies development, inoceramid paleontology and stratigraphy. *Acta Geologica Polonica*, 42(1-2): 1-122.
- Walaszczyk R., Kopaeich L. F. & Beniamovski V. N. 2013. Inoceramid and foraminiferal record and biozonation of the Turonian and Coniacian (Upper Cretaceous) of the Mangyshlak Mts., western Kazakhstan. *Acta Geologica Polonica*, 63(4): 469-487.
- Wilmsen M. & Nagm E. 2012. Depositional environments and facies development of the Cenomanian–Turonian Galala and Maghra el Hadida formations of the Southern Galala Plateau (Upper Cretaceous, Eastern Desert, Egypt). *Facies*, 58: 229-247.

- Wilmsen M., Berensmeier M., Fürsich F. T., Schlagintweit F., Hairapetian V., Pashazadeh B. & Majidifard M. R. 2020. Mid-Cretaceous biostratigraphy (ammonites, inoceramid bivalves and foraminifers) at the eastern margin of the Anarak Metamorphic Complex (Central Iran). *Cretaceous Research*, 110: 1-21.
- Woods H. 1912. The evolution of *Inoceramus* in the Cretaceous Period. *The Quarterly journal of the Geological Society of London*, 68: 1-20.
- Wright C. W. & Kennedy W. J. 1981. The Ammonoidea of the Plenus Marls and the Middle Chalk. *Palaeontographical Society Monographs*, 560(134), 1-148.